

Feedback to Modeling methodology draft

Presentation by CNR

Meeting: 9 Nov 2023, 10 am to 11:45 am CET (1:45h) CNR + UNIFI

Goal Diagram

Completeness:

What would be interesting would be to add **water as a resource**. Could it be a resource or an actual actor as part of the environment? If we put water as an actor, there is the risk to have too many actors. On one hand we have resources that are reachable, and nature that provides resources. We have resource units and resource systems. So having nature as an actor could imply that it provides resource units. We could think to **adjust the notation to include aspects that come from Ostrom**. In Ostrom there are actors, but are they only humans? Yes, they are.

In case you have the wireless infrastructure that monitors the environment, you would need **nature as an actor**, but if the system does not consider this, we do not need to include other actors. This can also be done with **layers**, a simple one with the minimum number of elements, and have then layers.

I think there is a task missing, since we **miss storage of the data** that they use for the forecast (incompleteness issue). The DSS is a combination of different components, so the wireless sensor network, it is not a tool of its own. Reply: from our viewpoint the DSS is just a software tool, but it depends on your definition.

Felicitas suggests having the **DSS infrastructure as the main actor**, and the other elements (WSN, DSS software, etc.) as included in the DSS infrastructure.

Comprehensibility: Hexagon is a goal? Somewhat, it is a quality. No other comments.

Effectiveness: comments are provided below.

Structural Diagram

Completeness: I think we should **change WSN infrastructure into DSS infrastructure**. Also there is an **interaction between the field and the DSS**, and especially the WSN component. The tools that are mentioned in the question are actually used to deploy and setup of the DSS, but other may be also sources for the DSS, once it is deployed: so, how to include these tools here? We are basically missing the components for the setup of the system: maybe this can be seen as another system: the system for the setup of the DSS. This also triggers the need to have **different actors** involved in the system, so it could be a way to highlight different actors, so the farmer and the technical in charge of deploying the system. This also highlights **different moments of the life of the system**. This has relevance also for the cost analysis.

Comprehensibility: should we add labels on the arrows? No, it is ok without labels. Should we have shown this diagram earlier? Probably having the diagram earlier could help. We could identify with **different colors digital and non-digital**. The tip of the arrows have different shapes, why? Answered. Is everything understandable? I do not know what do the three elements in each class mean: this is then explained. We need to provide clear instructions to the people who will compile it. What do you mean with compile it? We are asking the LL to use these schemes. Maybe we were talking with Manlio, if we should have done this, or if CNR has to do this. I would suggest asking them to do these themselves. But we have to decide. Another question: is there **software** to design these schemes? There are multiple software to be used. This point is rather complicated. So having tools used by others can be hard.

What about the link between irrigation tool and water resource: what is it? The water source is a passive actor that provides water and irrigation tool is the active actor. The irrigation tool calls the water, the actor is the tool. So the **meaning of the direction of the arrows** needs to be explained beforehand.

Effectiveness: the representation works, but we need to link them to the broader **conceptual framework**, and see whether this can be used to identify critical points related to the **cost**. But at the moment it is very clear now. With Felicitas and Mehdi we can see how to connect the costs.

Process diagrams

Completeness: no concerns.

Comprehensibility: no major comments at the moment. When we consider this in the broader framework, all this is simple and effective. Maybe we can test it again with our Manciano field visit.

Effectiveness: very effective overlapping between the two process diagrams before and after. The diagrams have two purposes: this is the basis for the analysis of the cost, and also the way to understand the needs for providers of the systems, but also useful for demonstration. Maybe a simpler version, but this last picture shows what was before and after the intervention, and this helps in the demonstration. It can be useful also to define cost and benefits.

Other comments: the level of the representation will depend on the living lab.